

PROVIDING MEDICAL CARE TO PATIENTS WITH INFECTIOUS DISEASES

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Annotation: Proper care for patients suffering from infectious diseases plays a key role in preventing the spread of infection, alleviating symptoms, and accelerating recovery. This article discusses the basic principles and procedures for caring for patients with infectious diseases, including precautions, hygiene procedures, condition monitoring, optimal nutrition, and psychological support. Special attention is paid to modern approaches to care that take into account the specifics of various infections and the individual needs of patients.

Keywords: patient care, precautions, hygiene, nutrition, psychological support.

Introduction.

Infectious diseases remain one of the main causes of morbidity and mortality in the world. Effective care for patients with infectious diseases is an important component of the infection control strategy aimed at limiting the spread of the pathogen, alleviating the symptoms of the disease and improving the quality of life of patients. This care includes not only medical treatment, but also a set of measures aimed at creating optimal conditions for recovery, taking precautions and preventing secondary infections.

The purpose of this work is to analyze and systematize the basic principles of caring for patients with infectious diseases, as well as to develop recommendations to reduce the risk of infection and improve the quality of medical care.

Principles of care for patients with infectious diseases.

The care of patients with infectious diseases should be based on the following principles.

Preventing the spread of infection: This is achieved by strict adherence to personal hygiene rules, the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), proper treatment of medical waste and disinfection of premises.

Symptom relief and comfort maintenance: Care should focus on relieving pain, fever, cough, and other symptoms specific to a particular infectious disease. It is important to provide the patient with a comfortable position, adequate rest and sleep.

Maintaining optimal nutrition and hydration: Infectious diseases are often accompanied by loss of appetite and dehydration. It is necessary to ensure that the patient has sufficient intake of fluids and easily digestible food rich in nutrients.

Monitoring of the condition and timely detection of complications: It is important to regularly measure the temperature, pulse, blood pressure, breathing and general condition of the patient. If there are signs of complications, you should immediately inform your doctor.

Psychological support: Infectious diseases can cause anxiety, fear, and feelings of isolation in patients. It is important to provide them with psychological support, provide communication with loved ones and provide reliable information about the disease and treatment.

Precautions in the care of patients with infectious diseases.

Taking precautions is critical to prevent the spread of infection among medical personnel, family members, and other patients. The main precautions include:

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Hand hygiene: Regular hand washing with soap and water or alcohol-based antiseptic treatment is the most effective way to prevent the spread of infection. Hands should be washed before and after contact with the patient, after removing PPE, after going to the toilet and before eating.

Use of personal protective equipment (PPE): The choice of PPE depends on the route of transmission of the infection. As a rule, gloves, masks (respirators), safety glasses or face shields and dressing gowns (aprons) are used. PPE should be put on before contact with the patient and removed after the end of care, while the removal rules must be followed to avoid contamination.

Isolation: Depending on the type of infection, the patient can be isolated in a separate room or in a specially equipped box. The rules for visiting isolated patients must be followed.

Disinfection and sterilization: Patient care items, surfaces, and medical equipment should be disinfected regularly. Medical instruments must be sterilized.

Medical waste disposal: Medical waste containing biological fluids and contaminated materials must be disposed of in accordance with established regulations.

The procedure for caring for patients with infectious diseases includes the following steps.

Assessment of the patient's condition: It is necessary to collect an anamnesis, conduct an examination and assess the general condition of the patient, identify the main symptoms and risk factors.

Care planning: Based on the assessment of the patient's condition, a care plan is drawn up that includes the necessary measures to alleviate symptoms, maintain nutrition and hydration, take precautions and prevent complications.

Care plan implementation: Planned care activities are being carried out, including.

Hygienic procedures: Regular washing, change of bed linen and underwear.

Medication monitoring: Ensuring timely intake of medications prescribed by a doctor.

Maintaining optimal nutrition and hydration: Offering the patient easily digestible food and sufficient fluids.

Relief of symptoms: The use of antipyretics, painkillers, expectorants and other medications as prescribed by a doctor.

Psychological support: Providing information about the disease and treatment, communicating with the patient and his relatives.

Monitoring of the patient's condition and assessment of the effectiveness of care: The patient's condition and the effectiveness of care measures are regularly assessed. If necessary, the care plan is adjusted.

Patient and family education: The patient and his family should be trained in the rules of care, precautions, and signs of complications so that they can provide the necessary care on their own and seek medical help in a timely manner.

Modern approaches to the care of patients with infectious diseases are aimed at personalizing care, using new technologies and actively involving the patient in the treatment process. These include:

Personalized care: Taking into account the individual needs of the patient, his age, concomitant diseases and psychological state when planning care.

Telemedicine and Remote monitoring: Using telemedicine technologies to consult with a doctor, monitor a patient's condition, and provide home support.

Use of information technology: The use of electronic medical records and other information systems to improve communication between healthcare professionals and coordinate care.

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Interdisciplinary approach: Involving various specialists in patient care, such as doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, psychologists and nutritionists.

Patient education and involvement in the decision-making process: Providing patients with information about the disease and treatment, encouraging their participation in decision-making related to their health.

Discussion

An important aspect of caring for patients with infectious diseases is the organization of the environment. It is necessary to ensure good ventilation of the room, regular wet cleaning using disinfectants and minimize the number of items that can become a source of infection. It is also important to create a comfortable and peaceful environment conducive to the patient's rest and recovery.

Special attention should be paid to skin and mucous membrane care. Regular washing, treatment with antiseptics and moisturizers help prevent the development of secondary infections and maintain the integrity of the skin. In the presence of pressure sores or other skin lesions, it is necessary to treat them in a timely manner and prevent complications. Monitoring the effectiveness of treatment and timely detection of side effects of medications is an integral part of care. It is necessary to regularly assess the patient's condition, measure vital signs and pay attention to any changes in his well-being. If there are signs of adverse reactions to medications, you should immediately inform your doctor.

Infectious diseases are often accompanied by loss of appetite and digestive disorders, so it is necessary to offer easily digestible and nutritious food. It is important to take into account the patient's preferences, but at the same time ensure that there is sufficient intake of proteins, vitamins and minerals necessary for the recovery of the body.

Psychological support plays a significant role in the recovery process. Infectious diseases can cause anxiety, fear, and feelings of isolation. It is important to show empathy, provide support, and create an atmosphere of trust. Talking, reading books, or listening to music can help distract from the illness and improve the patient's mood.

It is necessary to train the patient and his relatives in the rules of personal hygiene and prevention of the spread of infection. It is important to explain how to wash your hands properly, use antiseptics, and dispose of used materials. Understanding these rules helps to prevent infection of other people and contributes to a faster recovery of the patient.

Compliance with all of the above principles of caring for patients with infectious diseases allows you to ensure maximum comfort, speed up the recovery process and prevent the spread of infection.

Conclusion

Caring for patients with infectious diseases is a complex and demanding task that requires high professionalism, knowledge and skills from medical professionals. Proper care based on the principles of preventing the spread of infection, relieving symptoms, maintaining optimal nutrition and psychological support plays a key role in improving treatment outcomes and reducing morbidity and mortality from infectious diseases. Modern approaches to care that take into account the individual needs of patients and use new technologies to improve the efficiency and quality of care and improve the lives of patients with infectious diseases.

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